

Supplementary Material A

Details on Literature Search & Study Selection

A1. List of Study Eligibility Criteria

(Extension to section 2.2: Study Eligibility Criteria)

Primary studies had to fulfill nine eligibility criteria to be included in the meta-analysis (cf. Thielsch, Scharfen, et al., 2019). They needed to do the following:

- (1) Use an interactive and functional interface (e.g., software, website, prototype) that provided the necessary features for task completion.¹
- (2) Measure the perceived visual aesthetics of the interface as an independent or dependent variable and measure user performance as a dependent variable (see footnote 1).
- (3) Define perceived visual aesthetics (or equivalent designations) in accordance with this study's working definition.
- (4) Distinguish between at least two experimental conditions following a between-subjects or within-subjects design: In the experimental condition, participants are exposed to an aesthetically appealing interface; in the control condition, participants are exposed to an aesthetically unappealing interface.
- (5) Define the experimental conditions based on subjective evaluations of the interface's visual aesthetics by participants or experts. Studies defining interface aesthetics in terms of theory-based design concepts were not included.
- (6) Assess perceived aesthetics either in a preliminary study or in the original study, before or after interacting with the interface. For the aesthetic rating alone, it was deemed sufficient if the participants were presented with a screenshot of the interface, provided that they interacted with the interface before or afterward (see footnote 1).
- (7) Demonstrate a significant difference in the participants' aesthetic rating between the experimental conditions (i.e., the aesthetic manipulation needed to be successful). This implied that studies had sufficient data to test/determine the significance.
- (8) Be published in English or German.

¹ Criterion (1), (2), and (6) were refined during the process of study selection and, therefore, deviate from the preregistered eligibility criteria.

(9) Report sufficient data to extract/calculate the study effect sizes, or the study's authors had to provide the required data upon request. If essential data were missing from the studies, the authors were contacted via e-mail or academic networking platforms such as ResearchGate and LinkedIn, with a follow-up attempt if necessary. If no response was received or the requested information was unavailable, the study was excluded.

A2. Database Search Criteria

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
PsycInfo, PsycArticles, PSYINDEX via EBSCOHost	For PsycArticles and PSYINDEX, keywords (KW) are not available, so subjects (SU) are searched instead.	<p>(TI ("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR (AB ("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR (KW ("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability"))))</p> <p>(TI(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
		<p>Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR (AB(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR (KW(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit"))))</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
ACM Digital Library		<p>(Title:(<i>"aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical"</i> OR <i>"esthetic"</i> OR <i>"esthetics"</i> OR <i>"esthetical"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"esthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"visual aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"visual esthetics"</i> OR <i>"visually aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"visually esthetic"</i> OR <i>"visual appeal"</i> OR <i>"visually appealing"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical design"</i> OR <i>"aesthetic design"</i> OR <i>"esthetical design"</i> OR <i>"esthetic design"</i> OR <i>"attractive design"</i> OR <i>"beautiful design"</i> OR <i>"pleasant design"</i> OR <i>"emotional design"</i> OR <i>"attractiveness"</i> OR <i>"beauty"</i> OR <i>"pleasure"</i>) AND (Title:(<i>"performance"</i> OR <i>"user performance"</i> OR <i>"user behavior"</i> OR <i>"user behaviors"</i> OR <i>"user behaviour"</i> OR <i>"user behaviours"</i> OR <i>"usability"</i>))) OR (Abstract:(<i>"aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical"</i> OR <i>"esthetic"</i> OR <i>"esthetics"</i> OR <i>"esthetical"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"esthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"visual aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"visual esthetics"</i> OR <i>"visually aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"visually esthetic"</i> OR <i>"visual appeal"</i> OR <i>"visually appealing"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical design"</i> OR <i>"aesthetic design"</i> OR <i>"esthetical design"</i> OR <i>"esthetic design"</i> OR <i>"attractive design"</i> OR <i>"beautiful design"</i> OR <i>"pleasant design"</i> OR <i>"emotional design"</i> OR <i>"attractiveness"</i> OR <i>"beauty"</i> OR <i>"pleasure"</i>) AND (Abstract:(<i>"performance"</i> OR <i>"user performance"</i> OR <i>"user behavior"</i> OR <i>"user behaviors"</i> OR <i>"user behaviour"</i> OR <i>"user behaviours"</i> OR <i>"usability"</i>))) OR (Keyword:(<i>"aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical"</i> OR <i>"esthetic"</i> OR <i>"esthetics"</i> OR <i>"esthetical"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"esthetical interface"</i> OR <i>"visual aesthetics"</i> OR <i>"visual esthetics"</i> OR <i>"visually aesthetic"</i> OR <i>"visually esthetic"</i> OR <i>"visual appeal"</i> OR <i>"visually appealing"</i> OR <i>"aesthetical design"</i> OR <i>"aesthetic design"</i> OR <i>"esthetical design"</i> OR <i>"esthetic design"</i> OR <i>"attractive design"</i> OR <i>"beautiful design"</i> OR <i>"pleasant design"</i> OR <i>"emotional design"</i> OR <i>"attractiveness"</i> OR <i>"beauty"</i> OR <i>"pleasure"</i>) AND (Keyword:(<i>"performance"</i> OR <i>"user performance"</i> OR <i>"user behavior"</i> OR <i>"user behaviors"</i> OR <i>"user behaviour"</i> OR <i>"user behaviours"</i> OR <i>"usability"</i>))))</p> <p>(Title:(<i>"Ästhetik"</i> OR <i>"ästhetisches Interface"</i> OR <i>"ästhetische Schnittstelle"</i> OR <i>"visuelle Ästhetik"</i> OR <i>"visueller Reiz"</i> OR <i>"ästhetisches Design"</i> OR <i>"attraktives Design"</i> OR <i>"schönes Design"</i> OR <i>"angenehmes Design"</i> OR <i>"emotionales Design"</i> OR <i>"Attraktivität"</i> OR <i>"Schönheit"</i> OR <i>"ästhetisches Vergnügen"</i> OR <i>"ästhetischer Genuss"</i>) AND Title:(<i>"Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Leistung"</i> OR <i>"User Performanz"</i> OR <i>"User-Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Userperformanz"</i> OR <i>"User Leistung"</i> OR <i>"User-Leistung"</i> OR <i>"Userleistung"</i> OR <i>"User Verhalten"</i> OR <i>"User-Verhalten"</i> OR <i>"Userverhalten"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer-Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Benutzerperformanz"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer-Performanz"</i> OR <i>"Nutzerperformanz"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer Leistung"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer-Leistung"</i> OR <i>"Benutzerleistung"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer Leistung"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer-Leistung"</i> OR <i>"Nutzerleistung"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer Verhalten"</i> OR <i>"Benutzer-Verhalten"</i> OR <i>"Benutzerverhalten"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer Verhalten"</i> OR <i>"Nutzer-Verhalten"</i> OR</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
		<p>"Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR (Abstract:("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND Abstract:("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR (Keyword:("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND Keyword:("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit"))</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
Scopus		<p>TITLE-ABS-KEY(({aesthetic} OR {aesthetics} OR {aesthetical} OR {esthetic} OR {esthetics} OR {esthetical} OR {aesthetical interface} OR {esthetical interface} OR {visually aesthetic} OR {visual aesthetics} OR {visually esthetic} OR {visual esthetics} OR {visual appeal} OR {visually appealing} OR {aesthetic design} OR {esthetic design} OR {attractive design} OR {beautiful design} OR {pleasant design} OR {emotional design} OR {attractiveness} OR {beauty} OR {pleasure})) AND ({performance} OR {user performance} OR {user behavior} OR {user behaviors} OR {user behaviour} OR {user behaviours} OR {usability}))</p> <p>TITLE-ABS-KEY(({Ästhetik} OR {ästhetisches Interface} OR {ästhetische Schnittstelle} OR {visuelle Ästhetik} OR {visueller Reiz} OR {ästhetisches Design} OR {attraktives Design} OR {schönes Design} OR {angenehmes Design} OR {emotionales Design} OR {Attraktivität} OR {Schönheit} OR {ästhetisches Vergnügen} OR {ästhetischer Genuss})) AND ({Performanz} OR {Leistung} OR {User Performanz} OR {User-Performanz} OR {Userperformanz} OR {User Leistung} OR {User-Leistung} OR {Userleistung} OR {User Verhalten} OR {User-Verhalten} OR {Userverhalten} OR {Benutzer Performanz} OR {Benutzer-Performanz} OR {Benutzerperformanz} OR {Nutzer Performanz} OR {Nutzer-Performanz} OR {Nutzerperformanz} OR {Benutzer Leistung} OR {Benutzer-Leistung} OR {Benutzerleistung} OR {Nutzer Leistung} OR {Nutzer-Leistung} OR {Nutzerleistung} OR {Benutzer Verhalten} OR {Benutzer-Verhalten} OR {Benutzerverhalten} OR {Nutzer Verhalten} OR {Nutzer-Verhalten} OR {Nutzerverhalten} OR {Anwender Performanz} OR {Anwender-Performanz} OR {Anwenderperformanz} OR {Anwender Leistung} OR {Anwender-Leistung} OR {Anwenderleistung} OR {Anwender Verhalten} OR {Anwender-Verhalten} OR {Anwenderverhalten} OR {Usability} OR {Gebrauchstauglichkeit} OR {Benutzerfreundlichkeit} OR {Nutzerfreundlichkeit}))</p>
Web of Science	<p>Author keywords (AK) were used for the search instead of Keywords Plus (KP).</p>	<p>TI= ("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR AB= ("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design"</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
		<p>OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR AK=(("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetical design" OR "aesthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability"))</p>
		<p>TI=(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR AB=(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
ProQuest Dissertations & Theses	Keywords are referred to as identifiers (IF). The default “full text only” setting was repealed.	<p>"Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR AK(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit"))</p> <p>TI(("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetic design" OR "aesthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR AB(("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetic design" OR "aesthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
		<p>"pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability")) OR IF(("aesthetic" OR "aesthetics" OR "aesthetical" OR "esthetic" OR "esthetics" OR "esthetical" OR "aesthetical interface" OR "esthetical interface" OR "visually aesthetic" OR "visual aesthetics" OR "visually esthetic" OR "visual esthetics" OR "visual appeal" OR "visually appealing" OR "aesthetic design" OR "aesthetical design" OR "esthetic design" OR "esthetical design" OR "attractive design" OR "beautiful design" OR "pleasant design" OR "emotional design" OR "attractiveness" OR "beauty" OR "pleasure") AND ("performance" OR "user performance" OR "user behavior" OR "user behaviors" OR "user behaviour" OR "user behaviours" OR "usability"))</p>
		<p>TI(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR AB(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten"</p>

Database	Specification on field codes	Search string in English and German
		<p>OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit")) OR IF(("Ästhetik" OR "ästhetisches Interface" OR "ästhetische Schnittstelle" OR "visuelle Ästhetik" OR "visueller Reiz" OR "ästhetisches Design" OR "attraktives Design" OR "schönes Design" OR "angenehmes Design" OR "emotionales Design" OR "Attraktivität" OR "Schönheit" OR "ästhetisches Vergnügen" OR "ästhetischer Genuss") AND ("Performanz" OR "Leistung" OR "User Performanz" OR "User-Performanz" OR "Userperformanz" OR "User Leistung" OR "User-Leistung" OR "Userleistung" OR "User Verhalten" OR "User-Verhalten" OR "Userverhalten" OR "Benutzer Performanz" OR "Benutzer-Performanz" OR "Benutzerperformanz" OR "Nutzer Performanz" OR "Nutzer-Performanz" OR "Nutzerperformanz" OR "Benutzer Leistung" OR "Benutzer-Leistung" OR "Benutzerleistung" OR "Nutzer Leistung" OR "Nutzer-Leistung" OR "Nutzerleistung" OR "Benutzer Verhalten" OR "Benutzer-Verhalten" OR "Benutzerverhalten" OR "Nutzer Verhalten" OR "Nutzer-Verhalten" OR "Nutzerverhalten" OR "Anwender Performanz" OR "Anwender-Performanz" OR "Anwenderperformanz" OR "Anwender Leistung" OR "Anwender-Leistung" OR "Anwenderleistung" OR "Anwender Verhalten" OR "Anwender-Verhalten" OR "Anwenderverhalten" OR "Usability" OR "Gebrauchstauglichkeit" OR "Benutzerfreundlichkeit" OR "Nutzerfreundlichkeit"))</p>

Note. Deviations in the phrasing of search strings result from different abbreviations of field codes, symbols for searching for exact phrases, and rules for linking terms. To ensure standardization between databases, wildcards and truncation symbols were circumvented by varying the spellings of words. For searching keywords, author-provided keywords were given preference over database-assigned keywords.

A3. Keyword- and Content-Based Screening of Title and Abstracts

(Extension to section 2.4.2: Title and Abstract Screening)

Due to the large number of unique articles ($k = 28,997$), we conducted the screening process in two phases: First, we performed a keyword-based screening using the systematic review tool Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016), then we did a content-based screening of title and abstract using the semiautomatic screening tool Research Screener (RS; Chai et al., 2021). Since RS's algorithm relies on screening study abstracts, any missing abstracts were manually retrieved from Google Scholar and added if available. Studies without accessible abstracts were excluded.

Keyword-Based Screening Using Rayyan

Using Rayyan, all studies not reported in English or German were excluded, as these had been erroneously exported from the databases. The language of each study was determined either by the "main language" field in the studies' metadata or, if not available, by the language of the abstract (i.e., studies with English abstracts were classified as English-language studies). Next, studies were preselected based on their study design. We excluded articles containing one or more of the following terms in their title or abstract, indicating an observational or theoretical nature: *review(s)*, *case study/studies*, *case report(s)*, *introduction*, *editorial(s)*, *commentary*, *comment(s)*, *call for paper(s)*, *qualitative study/studies*, *meta-analysis*, *meta-analytic*, *retrospective study/studies*, or *retrospectively*. These terms were directly translated to German and used to prescreen studies with German titles and abstracts. This resulted in the exclusion of an additional 7,145 records, leaving 21,852 studies to be screened.

Content-Based Screening Using Research Screener

For the content-based screening of titles and abstracts, we used a beta version (Winter 2022/Spring 2023) of RS (Chai et al., 2021). At this stage, the screening tool was fully functional (L. Ng, personal communication, October 27, 2022). As RS only supports English abstracts, studies with German abstracts were manually screened using Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016). When uploading articles to RS, the tool automatically checked for an appropriate length of each abstract and identified duplicates. Four studies were excluded because their abstracts either exceeded the character limit (over 30,000 characters) or were too brief (fewer than 100 characters) and no alternative abstracts could be retrieved online. These four studies were screened manually instead. Furthermore, RS identified 17 studies as duplicates, which were added to the previously identified duplicates. A total of 20 studies were incorrectly identified as duplicates by RS and manually reviewed for eligibility.

Fundamental for the RS's semiautomated screening process was selecting "seed articles," which Chai et al. (2021) defined as "papers that [...] exemplify the key inclusion and exclusion criteria" (p. 9). These articles were also used to validate the search strategy applied to the electronic databases (Ng & Chai, 2021; see section 2.3 in the main text). At least one seed article is required to initiate the screening process, but the algorithm's efficiency improves as more seed articles are uploaded (Chai et al., 2021). Notably, the algorithm's accuracy is not influenced by the number of seed articles, as demonstrated by Chai et al. (2021). For this meta-analysis, we selected seven seed articles that were previously used to validate the literature search. These articles were drawn from previous reviews or literature research on this field. Note that the seed articles were not necessarily included in the meta-analysis but were rather chosen because their abstracts described the inclusion criteria in a representative way (Chai et al., 2021).

After uploading the seed articles, RS ranks the articles by relevance and presents the top 50 most relevant articles in each round that need to be screened manually. Screening results (marked vs. non-marked abstracts) are fed back into the algorithm to re-rank and determine the next top 50 most relevant articles. This process continues until either all articles are screened or "an evidence-based threshold" is reached, ensuring that all relevant studies have likely been identified (Chai et al., 2021, p. 4). Most exclusions were due to the following reasons: Studies were off topic (e.g., examining aesthetics and performance in art, sports, or health), relied on qualitative methods, did not use an interactive interface (e.g., screenshots), did not assess perceived visual aesthetics as rated by individuals (e.g., aesthetics were solely based on design principles), lacked comparisons between aesthetic conditions, or measured only subjective performance outcomes (e.g., perceived usability). The title and abstract screening was conducted by the first author. When study exclusion was uncertain based on the title and abstract, articles were marked for full-text screening to ensure high sensitivity of decisions (cf. Lefebvre et al., 2023).

After 30 rounds ($k = 1,500$), the screening procedure was stopped due to diminishing returns, as described by Chai et al. (2021). After 16 rounds (i.e., $k = 800$ abstracts screened), no additional eligible studies were identified, indicating the "long tail" concept. This is an observation of a flattening curve with several consecutive rounds showing no marked studies (see Figure 1; K. Chai, personal communication, November 11, 2022). In total, 73 records were selected for full-text screening, while 1,427 were excluded, representing ~6.6% of

papers screened of the total 21,738 records.² The remaining 20,240 records were automatically excluded. This falls within the range found in Chai et al.'s (2021) sensitivity analysis, where all relevant studies were identified after screening 4%–40% of articles.

Figure 1

Histogram of Marked Abstracts per Screening Round

Note. The number of marked abstracts represents the number of articles considered eligible per round based on title and abstract screening, with 50 articles reviewed in each round. The decreasing number of marked abstracts illustrates the long tail concept by Chai et al. (2021).

A4. Hierarchical Structure of Exclusion Criteria

(Extension to section 2.4.3: Full-Text Screening)

The exclusion criteria were hierarchically structured as follows:

- (1) No interactive interface.
- (2) Flaws in the operationalization of variables, including (a) the absence of an aesthetic measurement, (b) lack of subjective aesthetic measurement, (c) contradiction to this study's working definition of aesthetics, and (d) lack of objective performance measurement.
- (3) Flaws in the experimental design, such as (a) the absence of experimental conditions, (b) conditions not based on subjective aesthetic rating, or (c) no significant difference between conditions.

² Of the total 21,852 records selected for title and abstract screening, 21,738 were screened using RS, while 114 were screened manually. Of these, seven served as seed articles for RS, and the remaining 107 were manually screened due to being unsuitable for the RS algorithm (e.g., language restrictions, duplicates, or abstracts of inappropriate length).

(4) Missing data for calculating effect sizes, which included inadequately reported results or data that were not available upon request.

Each study's point of exclusion was noted, resulting in a distribution across the criteria.